

Management of Pregnancy in a Non-Communicating Rudimentary Horn with Placenta Accreta Spectrum: A Case Report

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Keywords:

Rudimentary uterine horn,
laparoscopy,
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Abstract

Introduction: The non-communicating rudimentary horn is a rare uterine malformation, and pregnancy in this horn is exceptional. Diagnosing pregnancy in a rudimentary horn is challenging, particularly in asymptomatic patients; it is often discovered in the second trimester, usually at the stage of uterine rupture with hemoperitoneum.

Clinical Case: We report the case of a 21-year-old nulliparous woman referred for management of a 24-week amenorrhea pregnancy that had stopped growing at 15 weeks on a bicornuate uterus. The patient presented no clinical symptoms, and biological examinations were normal. Pelvic ultrasound revealed a 12 cm gravid right uterine cavity with a 14-week fetus without cardiac activity. The left horn was deviated and empty. Communication between the two horns could not be confirmed. Hysteroscopy confirmed the presence of a single permeable cavity (the left) connected to the cervix; laparoscopy confirmed the diagnosis of pregnancy in a rudimentary horn with a high likelihood of placenta accreta spectrum and allowed for the resection of this horn. The postoperative course was unremarkable, and the anatomopathological examination confirmed the placenta accreta spectrum.

Introduction

Uterovaginal malformations are relatively rare, affecting 1 to 5% of the general population [1-3]. Among these, the hemi uterus or unicornuate uterus represents 12% of such malformations. According to the ESHRE/ESGE consensus of 2013 [4], this condition is classified as U4: U4a with a rudimentary cavity and U4b without a rudimentary cavity. Pregnancy occurring in a

rudimentary horn is exceptionally rare, with an incidence of approximately one in 150,000 pregnancies [5].

Diagnosing a rudimentary horn pregnancy is challenging, especially in the first trimester. The risk of serious complications, such as cornual rupture with hemoperitoneum in the second trimester, is significant. We report a case of a pregnancy in a non-

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communicating rudimentary horn at 24 weeks of amenorrhea (SA), which had stopped growing at 15 weeks and was managed laparoscopically.

Case Report

A 21-year-old patient, who had one prior undocumented spontaneous early abortion, presented for an ultrasound at 12 weeks of gestation. The ultrasound revealed a pregnancy in a bicornuate uterus, with the pregnancy developing in the right horn while the left horn remained empty; the intracornual septum was visible.

At 15 weeks, the pregnancy ceased to grow spontaneously. No fetal abnormalities were noted, and the patient did not experience pain or bleeding. Despite abortive medical treatment to induce expulsion, the pregnancy remained in situ. The patient was referred to our department for further management.

Clinical examination revealed no functional symptoms. The patient had a history of a previous spontaneous miscarriage at 8 weeks of pregnancy, but the diagnosis of uterine malformation had not been made at that time. Gynecological examination found a single closed cervix with no vulva-vaginal abnormalities.

Pelvic ultrasound showed a stopped-growing pregnancy with a gestational age of 14 weeks in a distended right horn measuring 12 cm, while the left horn was empty with a thickened endometrium. A myometrial wall separated the two cavities, and only one serosa appeared to connect the two horns (Figure 1). A single cervix was identified, likely associated with the left horn (non-pregnant). It was challenging to determine whether there was communication between the two cavities. MRI could not be performed.

The patient was clinically and biologically stable. Hysteroscopy revealed a single cervical canal and a single empty left horn with a tubal ostium, with no communication to the right horn (Figure 2a).

Laparoscopy showed a gravid, distended right uterine horn of approximately 12 cm (Figure 2a), with developed superficial vascularization. The serosa appeared very thin and fragile, raising suspicion of placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) (Figure 2d). The left horn was small, deviated to the left, and separated from the right horn by a 3 cm muscular bridge (Figure 2c). The adnexa were normal, and there was no communication between the rudimentary horn and the cervico-isthmic part of the normal horn. The diagnosis of pregnancy in a non-communicating rudimentary horn (U4a, according to ESHRE/ESGE 2013) was confirmed.

Figure 2: Endoscopic Steps of Diagnosis:
a-Hysteroscopy : left uterin cavity; b-c Laparoscopy: right pregnancy horn (black arrow) separate with a muscular bridge (yellow arrow) to the left normal horn (white start); d- Thin serosa with a developed vascularization: suspicion of placenta accreta spectrum

Figure 1: Pregnancy in the Right Horn with a Continuous Muscular Bridge with the Left Horn

Figure 3: Identification of The Right Ureter (White Arrow)

Surgical treatment involved a right salpingectomy with coagulation using bipolar forceps. The broad ligament was opened, the right ureter was identified, then the pedicle of the gravid horn was identified and coagulated, and the muscular band between the two horns was sectioned with advanced bipolar forceps, one centimeter from the left horn. The horn was extracted in an endobag through an enlarged incision on the central trocar.

Postoperative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged after the third postoperative day with hormonal contraception. Pathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of placenta accreta spectrum with myometrial invasion.

Discussion

This case highlights the diagnostic challenges associated with pregnancy in a non-communicating horn. Initially, the diagnosis was a stopped-growing pregnancy in a septate uterus (U2, ESHRE/ESGE 2013), particularly given the absence of pain. The diagnosis of a gravid rudimentary horn was suggested by ultrasound and confirmed by endoscopy after evacuation treatments failed.

A non-communicating rudimentary horn is a rare congenital malformation resulting from incomplete unilateral development of the Müller ducts before the tenth week. It typically results in one normal horn with an isthmus and cervix and a malformed horn without a cervico-isthmic part, making it blind. According to Heinonen [6], the pseudo-unicornuate uterus is associated with urinary tract malformations in 38% of cases, primarily ipsilateral renal agenesis.

Rudimentary cavities rarely have a functional endometrium but can exceptionally host an ectopic pregnancy: one in 76,000 and 150,000 pregnancies [7]. This is attributed to retrograde migration of a fertilized egg via the ipsilateral tube into the rudimentary horn. Diagnosis of this malformation outside of pregnancy often occurs in cases of infertility, recurrent abortion, or chronic pelvic pain. Pelvic ultrasound can suggest the diagnosis, but its sensitivity is modest 26-33% [8-9]. MRI is the gold standard for classifying genital malformations and can also identify associated urinary anomalies [4]. In our case, the absence of dysmenorrhea, chronic pelvic pain, or menstrual retention despite a receptive endometrium is likely due to the lack of a uterine isthmus necessary for menstruation. The rare diagnosis of rudimentary horn pregnancy often occurs during emergency situations, with only 5% of cases identified before uterine rupture [10-12]. Laparoscopy and hysteroscopy were instrumental in confirming the diagnosis by visualizing a single cavity with a tubal ostium and a gravid rudimentary horn separated from the normal horn by a thin muscular band.

Laparoscopic treatment is appropriate if the patient is hemodynamically stable [13-14]. Resection of the horn is indicated in cases of progressive pregnancy to prevent uterine rupture and severe hemorrhage. It is important to don't cause any injury on the serosa, which is thin with significant vascularization, the risk of placenta accreta spectrum must be considered, as this increases the risk of hemorrhage: it's exceeds 10% in rudimentary horn pregnancies [15], necessitates careful surgical management. This risk is due to improper decidual response and abnormal development of the myometrium, leading to variable penetration of chorionic villi. While PAS can be suspected by Doppler ultrasound, MRI remains the most reliable diagnostic tool.

Conclusion

Pregnancy in a rudimentary horn is a rare condition with limited literature. Early diagnosis, preferably preconception or early in pregnancy, is crucial to avoid complications such as uterine rupture. Laparoscopy is effective for both diagnosing and managing the gravid rudimentary horn. The increased risk of placenta accreta spectrum must be considered during surgical management.

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